

Protein purification, phosphorylation over time and phosphomapping experiments to investigate the influence of ALK2 mutations on activity.

Proteins to be purified for MS time course experiment:

Aim:

Purify ALK2 mutants L196P, R258S, G328E and R375P.

Constructs:

ACVR1Z-c033 (L196P)

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ/*SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCSTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARARMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTTLTKIDNSLDKLTDC

ACVR1Z-c043 (R258S)

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ/*SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCSTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLSHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARARMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTTLTKIDNSLDKLTDC

ACVR1Z-c047 (G328E)

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ/*SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCSTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQEKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARARMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTTLTKIDNSLDKLTDC

ACVR1Z-c086 (R375P)

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ/*SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCSTSGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PPVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARARMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTTLTKID

/* indicates TEV cleavage site.

Expression:

Expression of all constructs was in insect SF9 cells inoculated for 96h before harvesting at 900g and freezing at -20C.

Purification:

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate all samples for 3 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice.
- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (aprox 40ml per tube).
- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21 k rpm for 1 hour.
- Incubate lysate with 2ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 45 min. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- (G328E and R375P only: Wash with an additional 50ml binding buffer)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.

Take 15ul samples to run on an SDS-PAGE gel.

- Pool fractions elution fractions W2 - E4(3) for each protein that expressed and add Tev protease and leave overnight at 4C. (Discard samples from proteins that did not express)
- Concentrate down samples to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 200 column using standard gel filtration buffer (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of the peaks. All gels are 4 – 12% gradient commercial gradient gels run for 50 minutes at 170V.

SDS Page and corresponding AKTA traces for the purification of ALK2 mutants by Size Exclusion Chromatography using a GF200 column.

Pool relevant fractions for use in future experiments. Flash freeze excess in liquid nitrogen and store at -80C.

MS time course experiment.

The following incubations were set up using L196P and R258S mutants of the ALK2 protein:

Proteins were thawed from storage at -80°C and concentrations assessed by Nano drop.

From the concentrations, appropriate dilutions were calculated to get a final concentration of 40 µM for all proteins in a reaction mix of 100 µL (volume made up with water).

A 'master mix' containing ATP, ions and DTT was made up and added to activate the reaction at the start of the experiment.

	Absorbance	Extinction coefficient	Concentration uM	volume for 100ul rx at 40uM
ACVR1 A04	41	58900	696.0950764	5.746341463
ACVR1 B02	28.03	58900	475.8913413	8.405280057
ACVR2A	22.05	51900	424.8554913	9.414965986
BMPR2A	20.5	46870	437.3799872	9.145365854
BMPR2Z	8.3	46870	177.0855558	22.58795181
SMAD1	5.1	35410	144.0271111	27.77254902

Stock concentrations of proteins for assay

Tube:	1	2	3	4	5	6
ACVR1 A04	6	6	6			
ACVR1 B02				8.5	8.5	8.5
ACVR2A	9.5			9.5		
BMPR2A		9.1			9.1	
BMPR2Z			22.5			22.5
SMAD1	28	28	28	28	28	28
Master Mix	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
Buffer	44	44.4	31	41.5	41.9	28.5

Volumes (ul) required for assay (total rxn volume 100ul).

	rxn vol 100
Master mix	10 rxn
ATP	2.5
DTT	25
Mg	25
Mn	10
(all at 100mM)	62.5

Amounts of solution needed for master activation mix for 10 reactions total.

Reactions were set up in a 96 well plate, the plate was spun to ensure thorough mixing before the reaction was started by the addition of 6.26 μL of master mix. 1 μL of reaction mixture was extracted from each experimental condition simultaneously using a 12 channel pipette at specific time points (0, 30s, 1min, 2min, 3min, 4min, 5min, 10min, 15min, 20min, 25min and 30min) and the reaction quenched with acid in 60 μL Mass Spec running buffer (water with 0.1% formic acid).

Mass spec analysis:

Intact mass was determined using a QTOF mass spectrometer. A C3 cartridge was used for HPLC prior to ionisation.

The resulting chromatogram was used to extract the appropriate spectra corresponding to protein elution peak from the C3 column. All spectra were extracted simultaneously. Deconvolution was undertaken between 10kDa and 50kDa across a limited m/z range of 600 – 3000.

Data was exported with a peak intensity for every Dalton of the deconvoluted spectra. The data was plotted using Graphpad prism 8.0.

To reduce background noise in the presented graphs only data in a 25 Da window was plotted centred on the known intact mass and subsequently on the phosphorylated masses. For SMAD up to 3 phosphorylations were plotted. For ALK2 up to 8 were plotted. Each time point was displaced from the previous time point by a fixed amount (20, 100000) to stagger the presentation of the results. The first five minutes of data were deemed to be most interesting and so only the first five minutes were plotted in this instance.

Phosphorylation on SMAD1

Phosphorylation on ALK2

Time course plots for phosphorylation of SMAD1 (top) and ALK2 L196P or R258S (bottom) in the presence of ACVR2 (left) or BMPR2 (right). Legend shows time point in seconds.

Phosphorylation mapping of proteins from freezer stocks.

Set up the following protein incubations at 200ul volume for 30 minutes at 4C:

Protein	Ex coeff	Abs	conc (uM)	Mass	mg/ml	40uM in 200ul	mg/ml final	mg in sample
SMAD1-c001	35410.00	4.32	122.00	24735.00	3.02	65.57	0.99	0.20
ACVR2-c046	51910.00	12.84	247.35	33975.00	8.40	32.34	1.36	0.27
BMPR2-c015	46870.00	11.60	247.49	40114.00	9.93	32.32	1.60	0.32
A1Z-c041	58900.00	13.61	230.98	38472.00	8.89	34.63	1.54	0.31
A1Z-c082	58900.00	5.13	87.10	37334.00	3.25	91.85	1.49	0.30

Stock concentrations of proteins for assay

Tube 1		Tube 2		Tube 3		Tube 4	
SMAD1-c001	65.57	SMAD1-c001	65.57	SMAD1-c001	65.57	SMAD1-c001	65.57
ACVR2-c046	32.34	ACVR2-c046	32.34	BMPR2-c015	32.32	BMPR2-c015	32.32
A1Z-c082	91.85	A1Z-c041	34.63	A1Z-c082	91.85	A1Z-c041	34.63
Master mix	16.00		16.00		16.00		16.00
Buffer	-5.77		51.45		-5.75		51.47

Volumes (ul) required for assay (total rxn volume 200ul).

Samples then flash frozen until mass spec facility was ready for them after phosphorylation was confirmed by intact mass.

Mass Spec facility then digested aliquots of each sample with pepsin, trypsin, chymotrypsin, elastin, and PK both with and without enrichment for phosphopeptides and undertook MS/MS analysis.

Peptide samples were then assessed using the mascot server for phosphopeptides using a custom database of the proteins known to be present in the sample. A mowes score threshold of 23 unless otherwise stated was used for determining which peptides to look at. In some rare cases a threshold of 19 was used. Peptides were assessed on mowes score, consecutive ions being present, neutral loss, mowes score difference and whether the phosphorylation could be unambiguously assigned.

This data can be seen in the excel spreadsheet attached to this zenodo post.

Overall a high coverage (>90%) of the proteins was seen with the combination of all proteases and enrichment strategies.

TUBE 1
SMAD1A-c001
MHHHHHSSMSPIILGYWKIKGLVQPTRLLLEYLEEKYEELHYERDEGDKW
RNKKFELGLEFPNLPPYIDGDKVLTQSMAIIRYIADKHNMLGGCPKERA
ISMLEGAVLDIRYGVSR IAYSKD FETLKVDFLSKLP EMLKMFEDRLCHKT
YLNQDGHVTHPDMFLYDALDVLVYMDPMCLDAFPKLVCFKRIEAI PQIDK
YKSSKYIAWPLQGWQATFGGGDHP PKSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAPPLPS
EINRGDVQAVAYEPEKHWCISIVYELNLRVGEAFHASSTSVLVDGFTDPS
NNKRNFCGLLGNVNRNSTIENTRRHIGKGVHLYYVGGEVYAECLSDSSI
FVQSRNCNYHHGFHTTVCCKIPSGCSLKI FNNQEFQALLAQSVNHGFETV
YELTKMCTIRMSFVKGWGAEYHRQDVTSTPCWIEIHLHGPLQWLDKVLTD
MGSPHNPISSVS
52942.6 24735

ACVR2A-c046
MGHHHHHSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMPLQLLEVKARGRF GCVWKAQLLNEYV
AVKIFPIQDKQSWQNEYEVYSLPGMKHENILQF IGAEKRGTSVDVLDWLI
TAFHEKGSLSDFLKANVVSWNELCHIAETMARGLAYLHEDI PGLKDGHKP
AISHRDIKSKNVLKNNLTACIADFLALKEAGKSAGDTHGQVGTTRYM
APEVLEGAIFNRQDAFLRIMYAMGLVWELASRCTAAGDPVDEYMLPFE
EEIQHPLEDMQEVVYVHKKRPFVLRD YWQKHAGMAMLCETIEECWDHDA
EARLSAGCVGERITQMQRLTNI
36497.9 33975.2

ACVR1Z-c082 (R206H)
MGHHHHHSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMPTNVGDS TLADLLDHSCTSGSGSLP
FLVQRTVAHQITLLECVGKGRYGEVWRGSGWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFR
ETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSSTQLWLI THYHEMGS LYDYLQL
TTLDTVSLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQKPAIAHRDLKSKNIVLKKN
GQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNNPRVGTGRYMAPEVLDDET IQVDCFD
SYKRVDIWAFGLVWLEVARRMVSNGLIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPS FEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFS DPTLTSLAKLMKECWYQNP SARLTALRIKKTLT
ID
39856.6 37333.9

Tube 3
SMAD1A-c001
MHHHHHSSMSPIILGYWKIKGLVQPTRLLLEYLEEKYEELHYERDEGDKW
RNKKFELGLEFPNLPPYIDGDKVLTQSMAIIRYIADKHNMLGGCPKERA
ISMLEGAVLDIRYGVSR IAYSKD FETLKVDFLSKLP EMLKMFEDRLCHKT
YLNQDGHVTHPDMFLYDALDVLVYMDPMCLDAFPKLVCFKRIEAI PQIDK
YKSSKYIAWPLQGWQATFGGGDHP PKSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAPPLPS
EINRGDVQAVAYEPEKHWCISIVYELNLRVGEAFHASSTSVLVDGFTDPS
NNKRNFCGLLGNVNRNSTIENTRRHIGKGVHLYYVGGEVYAECLSDSSI
FVQSRNCNYHHGFHTTVCCKIPSGCSLKI FNNQEFQALLAQSVNHGFETV
YELTKMCTIRMSFVKGWGAEYHRQDVTSTPCWIEIHLHGPLQWLDKVLTD
MGSPHNPISSVS
52942.6 24735

BMPR2A-c015
MLTGDRKQGLHSMNMMEAAASEPDLDLNKLLELIGRGRYGA VYKGS LD
ERPVAVKVFSFANRQNF INEKNI YRVP LMEHDNIARF IVGDERVTADGRM
EYLVMEYYPNGSLCKYLSLHSDWVSSCR LAHSVTRGLAYLHTELPRGD
HYKPAISHRDLNSRNVLVKNQDGT CVISDFGLSMRLTGNRLVRPGEEDNAA
ISEVGTIRYMAPEVLEGA VNL RDCE SALKQVDMYALGLI YWEIFMRCDDL
FPGESVPEYQMAFQTEVGNHPTFEDMQVLVSRKQRPKPEAWKENS LAV
RSLKETIEDCWDQDAEARLTAQCAEERMAELMIWERNKSVSPTAHHHHH
H
40113.7 40113.7

ACVR1Z-c082 (R206H)
MGHHHHHSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMPTNVGDS TLADLLDHSCTSGSGSLP
FLVQRTVAHQITLLECVGKGRYGEVWRGSGWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFR
ETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSSTQLWLI THYHEMGS LYDYLQL
TTLDTVSLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQKPAIAHRDLKSKNIVLKKN
GQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNNPRVGTGRYMAPEVLDDET IQVDCFD
SYKRVDIWAFGLVWLEVARRMVSNGLIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPS FEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFS DPTLTSLAKLMKECWYQNP SARLTALRIKKTLT
ID
39856.6 37333.9

Tube 2
SMAD1A-c001
MHHHHHSSMSPIILGYWKIKGLVQPTRLLLEYLEEKYEELHYERDEGDKW
RNKKFELGLEFPNLPPYIDGDKVLTQSMAIIRYIADKHNMLGGCPKERA
ISMLEGAVLDIRYGVSR IAYSKD FETLKVDFLSKLP EMLKMFEDRLCHKT
YLNQDGHVTHPDMFLYDALDVLVYMDPMCLDAFPKLVCFKRIEAI PQIDK
YKSSKYIAWPLQGWQATFGGGDHP PKSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAPPLPS
EINRGDVQAVAYEPEKHWCISIVYELNLRVGEAFHASSTSVLVDGFTDPS
NNKRNFCGLLGNVNRNSTIENTRRHIGKGVHLYYVGGEVYAECLSDSSI
FVQSRNCNYHHGFHTTVCCKIPSGCSLKI FNNQEFQALLAQSVNHGFETV
YELTKMCTIRMSFVKGWGAEYHRQDVTSTPCWIEIHLHGPLQWLDKVLTD
MGSPHNPISSVS
52942.6 24735

ACVR2A-c046
MGHHHHHSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMPLQLLEVKARGRF GCVWKAQLLNEYV
AVKIFPIQDKQSWQNEYEVYSLPGMKHENILQF IGAEKRGTSVDVLDWLI
TAFHEKGSLSDFLKANVVSWNELCHIAETMARGLAYLHEDI PGLKDGHKP
AISHRDIKSKNVLKNNLTACIADFLALKEAGKSAGDTHGQVGTTRYM
APEVLEGAIFNRQDAFLRIMYAMGLVWELASRCTAAGDPVDEYMLPFE
EEIQHPLEDMQEVVYVHKKRPFVLRD YWQKHAGMAMLCETIEECWDHDA
EARLSAGCVGERITQMQRLTNI
36497.9 33975.2

ACVR1Z-c041 (Q207E)
MGHHHHHSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMPTNVGDS TLADLLDHSCTSGSGSLP
FLVQRTVAREITLLECVGKGRYGEVWRGSGWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFR
ETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSSTQLWLI THYHEMGS LYDYLQL
TTLDTVSLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQKPAIAHRDLKSKNIVLKKN
GQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNNPRVGTGRYMAPEVLDDET IQVDCFD
SYKRVDIWAFGLVWLEVARRMVSNGLIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPS FEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFS DPTLTSLAKLMKECWYQNP SARLTALRIKKTLT
ID
40994.9 38472.2

Tube 4
SMAD1A-c001
MHHHHHSSMSPIILGYWKIKGLVQPTRLLLEYLEEKYEELHYERDEGDKW
RNKKFELGLEFPNLPPYIDGDKVLTQSMAIIRYIADKHNMLGGCPKERA
ISMLEGAVLDIRYGVSR IAYSKD FETLKVDFLSKLP EMLKMFEDRLCHKT
YLNQDGHVTHPDMFLYDALDVLVYMDPMCLDAFPKLVCFKRIEAI PQIDK
YKSSKYIAWPLQGWQATFGGGDHP PKSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAPPLPS
EINRGDVQAVAYEPEKHWCISIVYELNLRVGEAFHASSTSVLVDGFTDPS
NNKRNFCGLLGNVNRNSTIENTRRHIGKGVHLYYVGGEVYAECLSDSSI
FVQSRNCNYHHGFHTTVCCKIPSGCSLKI FNNQEFQALLAQSVNHGFETV
YELTKMCTIRMSFVKGWGAEYHRQDVTSTPCWIEIHLHGPLQWLDKVLTD
MGSPHNPISSVS
52942.6 24735

BMPR2A-c015
MLTGDRKQGLHSMNMMEAAASEPDLDLNKLLELIGRGRYGA VYKGS LD
ERPVAVKVFSFANRQNF INEKNI YRVP LMEHDNIARF IVGDERVTADGRM
EYLVMEYYPNGSLCKYLSLHSDWVSSCR LAHSVTRGLAYLHTELPRGD
HYKPAISHRDLNSRNVLVKNQDGT CVISDFGLSMRLTGNRLVRPGEEDNAA
ISEVGTIRYMAPEVLEGA VNL RDCE SALKQVDMYALGLI YWEIFMRCDDL
FPGESVPEYQMAFQTEVGNHPTFEDMQVLVSRKQRPKPEAWKENS LAV
RSLKETIEDCWDQDAEARLTAQCAEERMAELMIWERNKSVSPTAHHHHH
H
40113.7 40113.7

ACVR1Z-c041 (Q207E)
MGHHHHHSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMPTNVGDS TLADLLDHSCTSGSGSLP
FLVQRTVAREITLLECVGKGRYGEVWRGSGWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFR
ETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSSTQLWLI THYHEMGS LYDYLQL
TTLDTVSLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQKPAIAHRDLKSKNIVLKKN
GQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNNPRVGTGRYMAPEVLDDET IQVDCFD
SYKRVDIWAFGLVWLEVARRMVSNGLIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPS FEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFS DPTLTSLAKLMKECWYQNP SARLTALRIKKTLT
ID
40994.9 38472.2

Ms/Ms phosphomapping coverage of each tube shown in red across all enzyme and enrichment strategies.